

Integration of Zero Defect as a Strategy to Improve the Quality of Educators

Ega Purwaningsih*, Masduki Ahmad, Desi Rahmawati
Department of Education Management
Universitas Negeri Jakarta
Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:- Education on the formation of Women Police Officers is organized by the Women Police School (Sepolwan) and the success of educational goals in Sepolwan depends on the human resources owned, especially educators as an important factor in education and the implementation of learning so that it requires qualified educators. This research uses a descriptive method of analysis and literature review, namely by describing the facts that occur or developing phenomena related to the quality of educators and how strategies to improve the quality of educators at the Women Police School (Sepolwan). The purpose of this study is to find out and analyze the quality of educators and establish strategies for improving the quality of educators at the Women Police School (Sepolwan) in order to create professional policewomen. The data collection methods used are interviews, observations, and documentation and use concept triangulation to compare research results through checking supporting references related to quality improvement strategies, educators, and zero defects. Based on the results of research and discussions that have been carried out, it can be concluded that first, the quality of educators at the Police School for Women (Sepolwan) is still low, this is due to the lack of work motivation which causes the implementation of their duties as educators is still not carried out optimally and the motivation to achieve achievements and self-development is still low so that the quality of educators needs to be improved. Second, based on the results of this study, a strategy was established to improve the quality of educators, namely by integrating zero defects as a strategy to improve the quality of educators at the Police School (Sepolwan).

Keywords:- Zero Defect, Quality Improvement, Educators

I. INTRODUCTION

The Police of the Republic of Indonesia have the duty and responsibility to improve the quality of professional, modern, and reliable police human resources and are required to always be able to keep up with the impact of change. Development by optimizing police education, especially education on the formation of Women Police Officers held at the Women Police School (Sepolwan). In carrying out the duties and tools of the state that provide protection and services to the community, the existence of Police is always together and integrated with the community, as well as the community's assessment of the performance of the Police of

the Republic of Indonesia in terms of performance in carrying out their duties as well as possible [1]. The success of educational objectives in the women police school depends on human resources, namely the principal of the women police school, educators, administrative personnel, and other educational personnel in managing the organizational culture of the Women Police School [2].

Anam revealed that to realize qualified Police personnel of the Republic of Indonesia, of course, breakthroughs are needed in the world of Police Education of the Republic of Indonesia, as is known in article 1 of Law No. 20 of 2003, concerning the Education System it is stated that Educators are educational personnel who are qualified as educators, lecturers, counselors, learning assistants, trainer, tutors, instructors, facilitators, and other designations that are by its specificity, as well as participating in organizing education [3]. Educators must be able to maximize their knowledge by paying attention to student development, to be able to place various substations of differences in learning experiences, differences in language and culture, learning styles, talents, and intelligence as the basis for implementing various teaching strategies. Based on this, in this case, the educators or Gadik at the Women's Police School are an important component in the implementation of the existing learning process, where educators have the task of planning, carrying out the learning process, assessing learning outcomes, conducting guidance and training as well as conducting research and community service. In Sepolwan, educators are coordinated and supervised by the School Educators Section of the woman police school [4].

The existence of the Women Police School as an Educational Institution of the Republic of Indonesia has a duty to develop quality human resources [5]. Then in the world of education, Sepolwan educational institutions are no exception, quality is a very important issue for an educational institution to produce good output. The quality of school education generally includes the quality of input, process, and output education. Educational inputs are declared of educational quality if they are ready to process, then the process is a series of activities to produce outputs, and later outputs are declared to be of educational quality if the academic and non-academic learning outcomes of students are high [6]. Based on this, it is clear that the quality of school education is based on the readiness of students and educators to process learning so that in the end academic and non-academic learning outcomes are high and graduates can be

absorbed in the world of work because the understanding of the quality of school education is graduates who can work well and professionally in the world of work.

Improving the quality of school education is a systematic process or method that continuously needs to be carried out to improve the teaching and learning process so that school goals can be achieved more effectively and efficiently, as well as quality. Sumadinata states that the quality of school education is focused on the quality of graduate education, therefore to produce graduates with quality education, the educational process must be of educational quality as well. A quality education process is a form of support for various aspects of education, including the support of leaders, education staff, educators, counselors, facilities and infrastructure, facilities, media, adequate learning resources, appropriate management, and a supportive environment [7]. From these various aspects, educators are a very decisive aspect to improve the quality of human resources through education, because in the implementation of learning the role of educators is very large to achieve learning objectives and education is carried out in the order of how the quality of education and learning outcomes lies in how educators carry out their duties with full responsibility and refer to basic values life and values of the educational process in the direction of ideal and beneficial conditions for learners [5].

The data on the achievement of School Examinations, School Examination rankings, and education quality report cards, shows low results, and the most need to be highlighted, especially on the standards of educators and education personnel who have very low scores due to the development of unprogrammed educators and staff, insufficient principal supervision, and lack of motivation of educators in carrying out their work as an educator. Based on interviews conducted with supervisors during the activities of the Educators Working Group (KKG), it was found that 1) The effectiveness of the principal's leadership still obtained a score of 45 out of 100 which indicates that it is still low. 2) About 50% of the learning process looks less effective in using its time, for example in a break of almost 30 minutes and still uses the old method of not involving children and educators are still central to learning. 3) Facilities and infrastructure in Sepolwan according to the education quality report card obtained an average of 4.26 which indicates that it is still low, and its use or use has not been able to use optimally. 4) The implementation of the principal's supervision activities is carried out only as a formality. 5) The lack of motivation of educators is that in classroom learning there are still many educators who teach conventionally, especially educators who are about to retire, learning have felt comfortable in the old ways. The creativity of educators in learning is still low, even though there are currently many cooperative learning models offered so that learning can be active, creative, effective, and fun.

Based on the above, it is known in the Regulation of the Chief of Police of the Republic of Indonesia No. 4/2010 Article 28 and 31 concerning the Education System of the National Police of the Republic of Indonesia relating to

educators, stated that educators are in charge of: a) Planning, implementing and evaluating the learning process; b) Conduct guidance, counseling, and training; and c) Conduct research in their field. The ability of educators is related to making POAC (Planning, Organizing, Actuating, and Controlling), namely their ability to carry out the learning process, their ability to evaluate learning outcomes, and the ability to develop students in actualizing their various potentials. Then police education at the Women's Police School aims to be able to produce students who are ultimately able to become good state servants to care for the community and educators of the Sepolwan Police of the Republic of Indonesia have a strategic role to produce quality young policewomen who can compete with the police force who are male and other armed forces, but that strategic role will run optimally according to their function if these educators have high performance[5]. Therefore, educators need to increase their potential and professionalism in teaching so that they can achieve the goals of education and become the importance of research on the quality of education based on that quality is not something that happens suddenly and appears by itself in front of educators [8], [9].

Based on this background, research was conducted on "Zero Defect Integration as a Strategy for Improving the Quality of Educators" at the Women's Police School (Sepolwan). The question in this study is how the quality of educators is and how the strategy of improving the quality of educators through zero defects in Sepolwan so that this research can be used to add knowledge related to the field of quality of education Furthermore, the results of this research can also be used as a guide for educational institutions, especially Sepolwan and other educational institutions that want to take advantage of the results of this research to improve the quality of its educational institutions.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses a descriptive method of analysis and literature review, namely by describing the facts that occur or developing phenomena related to the quality of educators and how strategies to improve the quality of educators at the Women Police School (Sepolwan) through references related to quality improvement. The purpose of this study is to find out and analyze the quality of educators and establish strategies for improving the quality of educators at the Women Police School (Sepolwan) to create professional policemen. The data collection methods used are interviews, observations, documentation and use concept triangulation to compare research results through checking supporting references related to quality improvement strategies, educators, and zero defects.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of research at the Women Police School, it is known that educators do not realize the importance of supervision and even tend to avoid being supervised so that this causes a low quality of education provided during learning, the following are things that become low quality of educators, including: 1) Principal supervision is only carried out on average once a year only meets the demands of formalities, 2) Educators

do not make teaching plans seriously, the learning implementation plan (RPP) made is a copy and paste from previous years or from other schools without being adapted to students, 3) Learning implementation plans (RPP) made only as an administrative complement without being implemented seriously, do not maximize teaching aids when teaching, do not carry out follow-up after assessment, and the use of IT in learning has not been maximized. This almost happened throughout Sepolwan in the area of the Indonesian Police education and training institutions, then these issues were also strengthened by interviews conducted by researchers from several educators on research and talks among educators at each meeting of the Educator Working Group (KKG).

Based on the above, educators at the Women's Police School still do not carry out their duties properly it will have an impact on the quality of education because something can be said to be of high quality if it meets existing specifications as well as in the field of education. The definition of quality itself about quality has two aspects, namely first, is to adjust to specifications. Then the second is to meet customer needs [10]. The factors related to the quality of learning are first, student readiness, second, the ability of professional educators and cooperation in school organizations, third is the curriculum which includes the relevance of the content and operation of the learning process, and fourth, namely facilities and infrastructure including adequacy and effectiveness in supporting the learning process [11].

Another factor that also affects the quality of school education in the implementation of learning is the work motivation of educators which is the most dominant and most important factor in formal education in general because for students educators are often used as exemplary figures and even become figures of self-identification and will affect the learning process, and are factors that greatly affect the achievement of educational goals. In addition to factors from learners and other facilities. The success of the implementation of education is largely determined by the readiness of educators in preparing their students through teaching and learning activities. However, the strategic position of educators to improve the quality of education results is strongly influenced by the professional abilities of educators and the quality of education performance. In that regard, according to Mulyasa [12] reveals that motivation is one of the factors that help determine the effectiveness of work. The higher the motivation a person has, the better his performance will be.

Based on the results of the study, it is known that the work motivation of educators in Sepolwan has not matched expectations and reality. Evidence that the motivation for the work of educators has not been as expected is based on the results of the Principal's Working Group (KKKS) meeting submitted by the principal through the board of educators meeting, it is stated that the presence of educators to school and class is often late and leaves the classroom ahead of the end of the lesson. 90% of educators in Sepolwan do not make teaching preparations that are by process standards, because they only reprint the products of previous years' teaching preparation plans or printouts. This shows the lack of responsibility of educators in carrying out work. In the meeting, it was also stated that educators rarely check assignments and student results and do not create remedial and enrichment

programs. The presence of educators in each KKG Cluster activity also conveyed that the percentage of educators' attendance in KKG activities was only in the range of 60%-70%. Experience in the field and research surveys show that the desire and motivation of educators to achieve levels of work achievement and self-development also tend to be low. This is shown in every competition event such as competitions for outstanding educators, research on educational scientific papers, best practices, and others, which must be followed by educators. Based on the results of research discussions on the quality of educators at the Women's Police School (Sepolwan), a strategy is needed to improve the quality of educators.

Integration comes from the English nation "integration" which means a merger, then integration is a process of unification by connecting. Thus integration is a variety of things that exist used by being united into one so that something is created to get a goal [13]. Furthermore, the word strategy comes from the Greek, that is, *kaya* "strategos" which means military commander (in the democratic age of Athens). In the days of Athenian democracy, every army led by strategos always managed to win wars so the techniques and procedures for strategizing were studied by many other countries and called strategy (tactics strategos). Strategy is a set of ways to achieve goals, so that strategy becomes a logical approach that will determine the direction of action strategy is also defined as an incremental approach, that is, a pattern or plan that integrates the main objectives, policies, and sequences of actions of the organization into one in a cohesive whole [8], [14].

Regarding quality, it is known that the notion of quality can be seen from two sides, namely the normative aspect and the descriptive aspect. In a normative sense, quality is determined based on intrinsic and extrinsic considerations, based on intrinsic criteria, the quality of education is an educational product, namely humans who are educated according to ideal standards. Meanwhile, based on extrinsic criteria, education is an instrument for educating a trained workforce. As for the descriptive meaning, quality is determined based on the actual circumstances, for example from the results of the learning achievement test [11].

Quality is a structured process to improve the output produced and the ability of educational institutions to utilize educational resources to improve learning ability optimally and produce outputs that are as expected. This is because, quality is something real and can be felt by everyone, and quality or often called quality until now still experiences contradictions of understanding because, on the one hand, it can be interpreted as an absolute concept, and on the other hand it can also be interpreted as a concept relatively, a) Quality as an absolute concept: quality in the view of most people is understood as something absolute with good, expensive, and idealism that cannot be compromised. So in the absolute concept, quality is part of a very high standard that cannot be outperformed. Quality products are something that is perfectly made and at a high cost and make satisfied and proud owners. This shows that achieving quality is the result of efforts that demonstrate the highest standards. b) The relative concept of quality: quality can also be used as a relative concept. The relative definition views quality not as

an attribute of a product or service, but as something that is ascribed to that product or service. In the factor of improving the quality of education, the maximum involvement of educators, by increasing the competence and work profession of educators in seminars, workshops and training so that the results of these activities are applied in schools is very important. This is because educators are the spearhead in the field (in the classroom) who interact directly with students in the learning process. Therefore, to improve the quality of learning, an educator must have the necessary conditions in teaching to build student learning to be effective in class, as well as cooperate with each other in learning [15][16].

Based on the above, zero defects are one of the existing quality improvement strategies, because this strategy contains clearer and more realistic steps if integrated into the world of education to become a strategy that can be used by the Women Police School (Sepolwan) in helping to improve the quality of its educators.

The zero defect quality improvement strategy is a strategy created by Philip Bayard "Phil" Crosby who was born in Wheeling, West Virginia in 1926, he is an entrepreneur and author who contributes to management theory and quality management practice. Crosby began working in quality management from the 50s, where he first worked in medical institutions and organizations, where he dedicated himself to updating and innovating the administrative parameters of the organization. His first job in quality was that of a test technician in the quality department at Crosley Company in Richmond, Indiana early in 1952, then he left his previous job for a better position with a salary as an engineer at the Bendix Company in Mishawaka, Indiana in 1955, working on the RIM-8 Talos missiles. He also left the company after less than two years to become a senior quality engineer at The Martin Company of Orlando, Florida to develop the Pershing missile. It was in this organization that Crosby developed the philosophy of "Zero Defect", then Crosby published a book about his first line of business called "Quality is Free" and this book became popular at a time due to the crisis in North American quality. During the late 1970s and into the 1980s, it was the North American manufacturer that lost market share due to most Japanese products that had superior quality of its goods. Then, according to Crosby in Efendi (2021) there are four things that are absolutely (absolute) an integral part of quality, namely that: a) the definition of quality is the conformance to requirements, b) the system of quality is prevention (The system of quality is prevention), c) the performance standard is flawless (The performance standard is zero defects), d) the measure of quality is the price of nonconformance [17].

Philip B. Crosby has gone to great lengths to emphasize that "Zero Defect" is a concept that can be realized, even if it is difficult. Crosby's quality improvement strategy is one of the most detailed and practical directions, and Crosby's approach can be applied as an activity plan. In his book, entitled "Quality Is Free", Crosby outlines his opinion that a systematic step towards realizing quality will result in good quality. The austerity of an institution will come naturally when it does everything right. Zero defects are the main and controversial contribution of Crosby's thoughts on quality, this idea is very powerful and also this idea is a commitment to always succeed and eliminate failures, because for him there

is only one standard, and that standard is perfection [17]. The idea is pure prevention and he is convinced that work without being wrong is a very possible thing. Other quality theorists such as Deming and Juran do not believe that this is an easy goal. They argue that the closer a person is to "Zero Defect", the more difficult it will be for him to eliminate errors as suggested by Juran that a certain point of the self-adjustment stage is the required stage. In the world of education, the "Zero Defect" method wants all students to be successful and develop their potential. Therefore, the task of improving quality in education is to build systems and structures that ensure the realization of this. This concept of "Zero Defect" was originally applied in the aerospace and defense fields, and 30 years later zero defects are used in the automotive world, and the ultimate benefit of all of it is that zero defects have been applied all over the world [17].

Based on this, zero defect integration can also be applied to improve quality in the field of education, which in this case is in order to improve the quality of educators at the Women Police School (Sepolwan), the following are strategic steps to improve the quality of educators through zero defects that can be done, including:

- Management commitment. Commitment to leadership. Quality achievement initiatives are generally by the leadership and are communicated as policies clearly and understandably by all implementing elements of the institution, which in this case are educators.
- Quality improvement team. Form a quality improvement team in charge of formulating and controlling the quality improvement program for educators.
- Measurements. Make quality measurements, by determining the baseline data when the quality improvement program starts, and determine the desired quality standards as a benchmark. In determining quality standards, involve customers who in this case are students at Sepolwan so that their expectations and needs can be known.
- Cost of Quality. Calculating the cost of quality. Every quality of a product/service is calculated including: if there is a repetition of work, if something goes wrong, inspection/supervision, and test/experiment, it can be known.
- Quality awareness. Generating awareness of quality for educators involved in the learning process in Sepolwan.
- Corrective Action activities. Perform remedial actions. For this it is necessary to have a systematic methodology so that the actions it performs are compatible with the resolution of the problem at hand, and therefore it is necessary to create a series of team tasks in a careful agenda. During the implementation, regular meetings should be held so that feedback from them is obtained.
- Zero Defect Planning. Carry out zero defect planning from the leadership to the entire implementing staff including educators. This planning requires various preparations, including by holding quality assurance workshops to determine quality standards.
- Employ education. Hold training to find out their respective roles in the process of achieving quality, especially for educators.
- ZD (Zero Defect Day) Day. Hold a flawless day, to create commitment and awareness about the importance of developing educators

- Goal setting. Formulate goals to be achieved appropriately and must be measurable in success.
- Error cause removal. This means simultaneously making improvement efforts. One of these efforts is the opportunity for educators to communicate to their superiors which of their jobs are difficult to do.
- Recognition. There must be recognition of achievements not in the form of money but for example awards or certificates and others of the like.
- Quality Council. The quality board consists of experts who formulate quality standards.
- Do it over again. Do it over and over again, because the program achieves quality will never end.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussions that have been carried out on "Zero Defect Integration as a Strategy for Improving the Quality of Educators" at the Women's Police School (Sepolwan), it can be concluded that first, the quality of educators at the Women's Police School (Sepolwan) is still low, this is due to lack of work motivation, causing the implementation of their duties as educators is still not carried out optimally, it is shown that educators do not prepare planned teaching well, rarely evaluating learning, then the use of information technology in learning has not been maximized, the discipline of classroom attendance is still lacking so that it is often late or leaves class before the end of time, and attendance in Educator Work Activities (KKG) is only in the range of 60-70%, as well as motivation to achieve a low level of achievement and self-development. Second, based on the results of this study, a strategy was established to improve the quality of educators, namely by integrating zero defects as a strategy to improve the quality of educators at the Police School (Sepolwan) which includes 14 steps of quality improvement strategies, including 1) Management commitment, 2) Quality improvement team, 3) Measurements, 4) Cost of Quality, 5) Quality awareness, 6) Corrective Action, 7) Zero Defect Planning, 8) Employ education, 9) Zero Defect Day, 10) Goal setting, 11) Error cause removal, 12) Recognition, 13) Quality Council, and finally step 14) Do it over again.

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